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TEACHERS PERCEPTION TOWARDS HRD CLIMATE: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

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Abstract

Proficient and motivated employees are the greatest assets of any organisation. The proficiency of employees plays a vital role in the context of the diverse challenges faced by the present date organisations. Talent management, employee engagement and employee retention have become the key concerns of HRD professionals. In order to generate, maintain and develop their competencies, the employees should be provided with an adequate opportunities as well as motivation for fostering a supportive and favourable climate. In the stream of studies carried out by various researchers in the field of HRD climate the present paper is moderate effort in this direction aimed at assessing the perceived views of school teachers in six private schools of district Srinagar. Teacher who occupy the most prestigious place in every society act as an essential catalyst in the development of an elegant society and in shaping the behaviour of the children. With high-quality teachers the civilization can move in the right direction.

Therefore the development of congenial HRD Climate for teachers in education sector has key role to play in the development of a nation. The present study was conducted in six private schools of district Srinagar on a total sample size of 140 teachers. The survey results on all variables taken for the present study reveal that the sample for study has a relatively good level of HRD climate. The result also suggests that Top management's commitment need to be focused towards overall responsiveness to HRD function.

Key Word: General climate, HRD climate, HRD-sub systems, OCTAPAC culture

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Introduction:

Swiftly changing technology oriented world and intensive competition have put forth the major challenges of survival and sustainability for the organisations of today. And those organisations that are capable of acquiring and utilizing the scarce, valuable and inimitable resources can only meet the present date competition (Barney, 1991). Similarly as per Dr. Birajit mohanty (2012) Human resource is an undoubtedly the most challenging and dynamic capital in an organization. They are the contributors to the intellectual capital, social capital and emotional capital of an organization. In this light Dev Raj Adhikari (2009) stated HRD as an important developmental program to ensure that the organization has an institutionalized way of developing, utilizing and committing human resources in order to meet current and future organizational challenges. HRD is more personnel-oriented than technology-oriented and believes that participation and communication would bring about greater commitment, efficiency, and growth of individuals Ajay Solkhe and Dr. Nirmala Chaudhary (2011). The vital importance of human resources can clearly be captured in the quotation made by the Managing Director of British Chrome and Steel who in 1998 stated: "There is no other source of competitive advantage; others can copy our investment, technology and scale- but not the quality of our people." In this preview Mahajan sates, "The human resource being the most vital factor of production and labour productivity, a positive, forward looking, human resource development policy is a *sine-qua-non* for the efficiency and effectiveness of employees" (Mahajan, 1996). The HRD has become one of the most important and prominent drivers of competitive advantage. Human resource development, or HRD as a concept, is a widely used to refers all those activities aimed at developing people within an organization. The term has different connotations as it may refer to development of human capacities with the aim of raising profit in business but also, especially in developing countries, with the aim of achieving personal and societal advancement. Human Resource Development (HRD) has been defined in the words of Chalofsky (1992) as "the study and practice of increasing the learning capacity of individuals, groups, collectives, and

organizations through the development and application of learning-based interventions for the purpose of optimizing human and organizational growth and effectiveness." As a function within an organisation, it "plays a principal role in enhancing the long-term sustainability of organizations and has the potential to help cultivate organizations that positively influence individuals, communities, society, and the environment" (Hatcher, 1999). According to McLean and McLean (2001) HRD is "any process or activity that, either initially or over the long term, has the potential to develop work-based knowledge, expertise, productivity and satisfaction, whether for personal or group/team gain, or for the benefit of an organization, community, nation, or, ultimately, the whole of humanity." The concept of HRD was formally introduced by Prof. Dr. Leonard Nadler way back in year 1969 in a conference organised by American Society of Training and Development as a series of organized activities within the specific period of time and designed to produce behavioural change. In the revised definition by Nadler (1984) states that HRD is an organised learning experience in a defined time period to increase the possibility of job performance and growth. In India, it was Larson & Toubro Ltd in 1975 among the private sector Company and BHEL among the public sector government companies that first introduced the concept of HRD with a motive of facilitating growth of knowledge workers.

In order to have competitive edge in the present turbulent business environment organisations need to provide their employees with an amiable climate so that they can contribute their utmost potential to perform current job demands and prepare for future challenges. However, the researchers conducted across the globe are inductive of the fact that a conducive HRD Climate goes a long way in developing , nurturing, and flourishing human capital in terms of their innate and unexplored competencies and capabilities so as to benefit both society at large and organisation in particular. In Indian context **Human Resource Development (HRD) Climate** concept was proposed by T.V. Rao (1999) who explain HRD Climate as the environment provided by organisations for the learning and development of its employees. This includes not only the

policies but also the HRD practices in an organisation. An instrument was developed by him to measure the HRD Climate by undertaking the three primary components/elements such as the top management's commitment to HRD (General Climate), the functioning of the various HRD subsystems /HRD mechanism, and existence of OCTAPACE culture. Whereas General climate highlights the extent to which the management of an organization has sincere intention, determined will and takes supportive actions for developing its manpower. HRD Mechanism being that component of the HRD climate which measures the extent to which the various subsystems of the HRD mechanism such as training, performance appraisal, potential appraisal, organisation development, feedback and performance coaching, career planning, rewards, employee welfare, quality of work life and human resource information systems are implemented seriously. And the OCTAPACE culture embraces eight factors namely, Openness, Confrontation, Trust, Autonomy, Pro-activity, Authenticity, and Collaboration and experimentation in an organisation. (Rao, 1999).

The success of HRD in an organisation depends, to a large extent, on the existence of a favourable HRD climate. As notably argued by T.V.Rao in the year 1999 that an organization that has a better HRD climate and processes is likely to be more effective than an organization which does not have. HRD climate is said to play a very important role in ensuring the success of any organization because it directly or indirectly affects the performance of the employees. Similarly it was argued by Prof.Karunesh Saxena and Pankaj Tiwari (2009) that if the HRD climate is favourable than the employees will contribute their utmost for the achievement of the organizational objectives. It is possible for management to improve the HRD climate by introducing the desirable changes in HR policies and practices.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

HRD embraces the development oriented activities of the organization for improving the efficiency of its valuable human resource. For an individual to perform productively, the climate

prevailing in the organization needs to be conducive for its development. Various research studies have been conducted to determine, analyse the factors affecting the HRD Climate and perception of employees regarding the prevailing HRD climate and few of them are cited hereunder.

Shakeel (1999) in his study of the HRD Climate of two Central Universities found that HRD Climate in both the universities at 'low' level, though the developmental climate in Delhi University is comparatively better than those of Jamia Millia Islamia University.

Rodrigues (2005) opined in his article entitled "Industry-Institute correlates of HRD Climate-Empirical study based implications" that a well-trained and a well-educated human resource contributes directly to the development of a country and to improve the knowledge, abilities, aptitude and values of human beings organized HRD practices should be followed.

Mufeed& Gurkoo, (2006) attempted to study HRD climate in universities and found poor HRD climate and employees dissatisfied with the prevailing HRD practices in the university.

Mufeed and Shah (2006) while examining the perception of 549 teaching and non-teaching employees on the existing status of HRD climate of 9 Indian Universities have concluded that the existing HRD climate in the university is not perceived to be satisfactory.

Vijaya Banu (2007) in his study A Study on HRD Climate with Special Reference to Public Sector Cement Corporation, concluded that to survive and excel in the new economy, the HRD climate is of crucial importance to the Indian public sector organizations.

Pooja Purang (2007) in a Comparative Analysis of HRD Climate in Public Private and Multinational Organizations concluded that the Employee perceptions regarding the Human Resource Development Climate are significantly better in the private sector and MNC in comparison to the Public Sector Organization.

Srimannarayana (2008) carried out a study to assess the extent of HRD climate prevailing in Indian organizations. He argues that a moderate

climate prevails in organizations understudy (59.61%) and more favorable HRD climate was in manufacturing sector (62.39%) than in service & IT sectors.

Purang (2008) argues that a favourable climate influences directly the behavior of managers in an organization which creates a sense of belongingness in them and also enables them to perform well.

Hyde et al. (2008) conducted an exploratory survey of HRD Climate in private sector banks. The survey suggested that the developing and maintaining the dyadic relations at work and supportive guidance should be provided by seniors to their juniors in creating a congenial working atmosphere which will also help in developing human resource in an organized manner.

Rao (2009) carried out a study on HRD climate in the thermal Power Station of Vijayawada in Andhra Pradesh and the study revealed that the HRD is a process which helps to develop and identify the keen potential of human force. He further suggested that the management in an organization should be generous and should also support their work force emotionally so that it will help the employees to work better and enable them to exhibit their knowledge and skills in a cohesive manner.

Ch. Venkataiah (2011) studied Correlation between HRD Practices and Employee Performance of Private Engineering Colleges in Hyderabad.

Solkhe and Chaudhary (2011) studied the Impact of HRD Climate over Job satisfaction measures to improve the Organizational Performance. Sample size chosen for the study was 100 managers out of which only 71 executives responded through a 38 items model questionnaire developed by Rao and Abraham for analysing the trends in HRD Climate. The managers in general showed a favourable attitude towards HRD Policies and practices of the organization. They were satisfied with the developmental policies of the top management as well as contented with their work and the organization as a whole i.e. level of job satisfaction was also good.

Subramani and Jan (2011) discussed the importance of the efficiency of human resource in the success of any organization in their published research paper. The authors emphasized their work over the study of organizational climate in IT industries of Chennai, authors suggested to improve the organizational climatic conditions to match the requirements of the organizational development.

Mukesh kumar parsahar (2012) carried out a study to assess the perception of employees regarding HRD climate prevailing in the shri vaishnav institute of technology and science a private college in indore on the basis of their age group and came up with the conclusion that there was no significant difference in the perception of the employees belonging to different age groups about prevailing HRD climate in the said institute.

Benjamin (2012) examined the relationships among human resource development climate (HRDC), organizational Citizenship behaviour (OCB) and voluntary turnover intentions (VTI) in Nigerian banks. The study found Nigerian banks management can reduce turnover and foster citizenship behaviour by ensuring that a favourable developmental climate exists within their organization.

Sekar, Muttiah and Santosh (2012) presented the HRD Climate of workers in Indian manufacturing companies. And found the existence of average climate for development in these organizations.

Dubey Pushkar and Surenthiran N (2013) carried out a study the result of which revealed that the HRD Climate in private schools of western Odisha is above average which indicates that there still exists a scope on part of management to raise HRD Climate so as to reinforce teacher's development.

Parveen choughale (2013) assessed the extent of HRD climate prevailing in higher educational institutions in Kolhapur district and found average level of HRD climate in higher educational institutions.

Significance of the study

“Education is a form of learning in which knowledge, skills and habits of a group of people are transferred from one generation to the next through teaching” John Dewey (1944). National educational policy 1998 rightly points out that students are positive assets of any country with high potentials to be developed with tenderness and care. It is impossible for any country to realize its educational objectives in absence of committed and competent teachers even if it possesses healthy physical requirements Noorjahan (2007). The teachers who are considered as the porters are the most imperative factor in shaping the behaviour of a child. They are the most essential or we can say life blood element in constructing a civilized and an elegant society. Therefore the development of teachers in education sector has a significant role to play in the development of a nation.

As has been rightly brought up by Mohammad Iqbal mattoo (2010), “As is the teacher, so is the nation.” The teacher being the central main character in the whole circle of educational process has a capability to bring constructive, productive, and quality education in the society because they are entrusted by the parents in deciding the destiny of their children Choooh (2005). Therefore, it becomes mandatory to ensure a congenial climate in every organization; and educational sector being no exception. It is against this backdrop that the study was carried in private schools of district Srinagar to assess the perception of teachers towards the HRDC.

Objectives of the Study

In the light of the above extant literature surveys the present study is poised to meet following set of objectives:

- i. To study the perceived views of Teachers on various aspects of general climate prevailing in their schools.
- ii. To study the extent of Teachers perception on HRD Process through OCTAPAC Culture.
- iii. To ascertain the perception of the Teachers on the prevalent HRD mechanisms in the sample study organisation.

Hypothesis

H0: There is a significant relationship between the three elements of HRD climate (general climate, OCTAPACE culture, and HRD mechanisms) in private schools of Srinagar district.

H1: There is not any significant relationship between the three elements of HRD climate (general climate, OCTAPACE culture, and HRD mechanisms) in private schools of Srinagar district.

Research Methodology

The present study has adopted *convenient sampling technique*. In the present study the population consists of the teachers engaged in private schools of Srinagar district. A sample of 150 teachers was randomly selected from 6 different private schools of Srinagar District. 38 item HRD Climate survey questionnaire developed by centre for HRD at XLRI, Jamshedpur was used for collecting data. This is the standardized and widely used instrument for HRD Climate survey. A total of 150 questionnaires were distributed in six (6) different schools covered in Srinagar district. The total number of filled questionnaire which were received back was found to be 145 so the response rate was found to be 95% approximately. Lastly, only 140 filled in questionnaires were selected for this study after rejecting 05 questionnaires for being inadequate in terms of required inputs.

Results and Discussion

Framework for data analysis:

Five point Likert scale was used to measure the perception of the teachers ranging from “1-5” (where 1= not at all true, 2= rarely true, 3=sometimes true, 4=mostly true, 5=almost true). The mean score of 1 indicates extremely poor and of 5 indicates exceptionally excellent/high existence of HRD climate in the sample for the present study. In order to make

interpretations easy the mean score were converted into percentage score by using a formula: percentage score= (mean score-1)*25. This assumes that a score of 1 represents 0%, of 2 represents 25%, of 3 represents 50 %, of 4 represents 75% and of 5 represents 100%. Thus, percentage score indicates the degree to which the particular dimension exists in the sample out of ideal 100.

The entire gamut of data collected have been analysed by using mean score, simple percentage and standard deviation, Karl Pearson’s correlation were used to test the level of significance.

Table 1: Test of Reliability:

Reliability	
Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.861	38

The above table shows the reliability test for 38 items. The value of Cronbach's Alpha was found to be 0.861 which suggests that the data collected is reliable for further analysis.

S.No.	General climate	MEAN	%	SD
1	The top management of this school goes out of the way to make sure that the employees enjoy their work.	3.3571	59%	1.36804
2	Top management of this school believes that human resources are an extremely important resource who should be treated more humanely.	3.4500	61%	1.25420
3	Development of teachers is seen as an important responsibility by the senior's at this school/institute.	3.7500	69%	1.17605
4	The personnel policies in this school facilitate employee development.	3.1214	53%	1.14721
5	The top management is willing to invest a considerable part of their time and other resources to ensure the development of the teachers.	3.4214	60%	1.33609
6	Senior officials/principal in the school takes active interest in their juniors and helps them learn their job.	4.0071	75%	1.00714
7	Employees lacking confidence in doing their job are helped to acquire competence rather than being left unattended.	3.6357	66%	1.14559
8	Officials/principal in this school believe that employee behaviour can be changed and the people can be developed at any stage of their life	3.8571	71%	1.04964
9	Teachers in the school are helpful to each other.	4.2214	80%	.97500
10	Employees in this school/institute are very informal and do not hesitate to discuss personal problems with their supervisors.	3.8214	70%	1.17692
11	Psychological climate in this school/institute is very conducive to any employee interested in developing himself by acquiring new knowledge and skills	3.7643	69%	1.04991
12	In these school/institute seniors guide their juniors and prepare them for future responsibilities and roles they are likely to take up.	3.7714	69%	1.04119
13	Principal/Director of this school/institute makes efforts to identify and utilize potential of the employees	3.9786	74%	.92501
18	Employees in this school/institute do not have any fixed mental impressions about each other.	3.3429	59%	1.30175
	Average	3.6786	67%	.54496

Table 2: General Climate

Data scoring, Data analysis and interpretations:

In assessing the top management’s commitment to HRD general climate, 14 corresponding items were identified in the questionnaire and the respondents’ perception in selected sample was accordingly scored.

Table 2: General Climate

Table 2 reflects the mean, percentage and standard deviation as well as the total average scores in respect of the general climate prevailing in the private schools of district Srinagar. As per table 2 below, the average mean score of 3.67 (67%) indicates existence of an average level of congenial general climate in the private schools of Srinagar district. The important factors contributing largely to the general climate than others are, item no.6, 8, 9, 10 and 13 with the mean score of (4.0071), (3.8571), (4.2214), (3.8214), (3.9786) respectively.

Table 3: OCTAPAC CULTURE

OCTAPAC (openness, confrontation, trust, autonomy, pro-activity, authenticity, collaboration) culture is essential for facilitating HRD. Openness exists when employees feel free to discuss their ideas, activities, and feeling with each other. By confrontation problems and issues are brought out into the notice with a view to solve them rather than hiding them for fear of hurting or getting hurt. Trust is taking people at their face value and believing what they say. Autonomy is giving freedom to let the people work independently with responsibility. Proactivity is encouraging people to take initiative and risk. Authenticity is the tendency on part of the people to do what they say. Collaboration is to accept interdependencies, to be helpful to each other and work as teams (Rao and Abraham 1986).

Table 3: OCTAPAC Culture

S.No	ITEMS	Mean	%	SD
27	Employees trust each other at this school/institute.	4.0643	77%	1.02635

28	Employees at this school/institute are not afraid to interact with their superiors to share their feelings.	4.0000	75%	1.16915
29	Employees at this school/institute are not afraid to express or share their feelings with their subordinates.	3.8500	71%	1.39333
30	Employees are encouraged to take initiative and undertake activities on their own without having to wait for instruction from seniors.	3.0071	50%	1.33301
31	Delegation of authority to encourage juniors to develop handling higher responsibilities is quite common at this school/institute.	3.3929	60%	1.01568
32	In the event of delegation of authority, juniors use it as an opportunity for development	3.7500	69%	1.09364
33	Team spirit is of high order at this school/institute.	4.1143	78%	.98248
34	In the event of problems cropping up employee discuss them mutually to resolve them rather than indulge in any blame game.	3.9571	74%	.95865
35	Seniors often discuss career growth opportunities of juniors with them at this school/institute	3.5143	63%	1.17825
36	Our school/institute’s future plans are made known to the senior staff to help them develop their juniors and prepare them for future.	3.8786	72%	1.08268
	Average	3.7529	69%	.63023

As indicative from the table 3, mean and percentage score of OCTAPAC Culture is 3.7529 and 69% respectively which indicates existence of relatively good level of OCTAPAC Culture in private schools of Srinagar.

TABLE 4: HRD MECHANISM – IMPLEMENTATION OF HRD SUB-SYSTEMS

This section examines the implementation of HRD sub-systems such as training, performance appraisal, Potential-appraisal, career planning, performance rewards, counselling and feedback, employee welfare for quality work life, job rotation etc.

According to table 4, mean and percentage score for implementation of HRD sub-system is 3.80 and 72% respectively which indicates existence of significantly good level of HRD sub-system in private schools of Srinagar.

Table 4: HRD Mechanism

S.No	ITEMS	MEAN	%	SD
14	Promotions in this school/institute are governed by the suitability criteria alone without any favouritism.	3.7500	69%	1.20027
15	This school/institute has established mechanism to reward employee's good work and contributions.	3.4000	60%	1.25692
16	Principal in this school/institute appreciates employee's good work.	3.9214	73%	1.14470
17	Performance appraisal reports in this school/institute are based on objective assessment without any subjectivity.	3.7357	68%	1.04304
19	Employees are encouraged to experiment with new methods and explore creative ideas.	4.3071	83%	4.46069
20	When any employee makes a mistake his seniors treat it with understanding and help him to learn from such mistakes rather than punish or discourage	3.8857	72%	1.16968

	him.			
21	Weakness of employees is communicated to them in a non-threatening way at this school/institute.	3.8857	72%	2.02533
22	When feedback is given to employees they take it seriously and use it for development	4.0571	76%	1.14911
23	Employees at this School take pains to understand supervisors or colleagues perceptions about their strengths and weakness.	4.1429	79%	.98603
24	Employees sponsored for training take it seriously and try to make it best use.	4.1929	80%	1.04500
25	Employees following training are encouraged to apply ideas learnt.	3.9786	74%	.97056
26	Employees are sponsored for training on the basis of genuine training needs.	3.7500	69%	1.08704
38	In this school/institute opportunity to work in different classes by rotation facilitates employee development.	3.6786	67%	1.07468
37	The welfare activities in this school/institute enable employees to harness their mental energy for work purposes.	3.9143	73%	1.07614
	Average	3.9000	72%	.72721

Table 5: Comparative Analysis of Three elements of HRD climate

Item no.	HRD Elements	Average mean Score	%	SD
1	General Climate	3.6786	67%	.54496
2	HRD Mechanism	3.9000	72%	.72721
3	OCTAPAC Culture	3.7529	69%	.63023
		3.7774	69%	0.6341

As discussed earlier HRD climate is grouped into three broad categories viz, 1.general climate, 2.OCTAPAC Culture and 3.HRD mechanisms. These elements can prove important instruments for organisational subtleties, growth and effectiveness, if implemented effectively. To

create an appropriate HRD climate in any organisation contribution of the three elements is of equal importance. Change can be brought in a systematic manner only by using General climate along with OCTAPAC Culture and introduction of HRD Mechanisms.

Table 5 above strongly depicts General climate with the mean score 3.6786 (67%), OCTAPAC Culture with the mean score 3.7529 (69%) and HRD Mechanisms with mean score 3.9000 (72%) are relatively touching towards existence of fairly good HRD Climate level (in the private schools of Srinagar District).

Hypothesis Testing

Hypotheses **HO**: There is a significant relationship between elements of HRD climate (general climate, OCTAPACE culture, and HRD mechanisms) in private schools of Srinagar district.

Hypotheses **H1**: There is not any significant relationship between elements of HRD climate (general climate, OCTAPACE culture, and HRD mechanisms) in private schools of Srinagar district.

Table 6: Karl Pearson Correlations test: inter comparison between the three elements of HRD Climate

		GENERAL CLIMATE	HRD MECHANISM	OCTAPAC CULTURE
GENERAL CLIMATE	Pearson Correlation	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)			
	N	140		
HRD MECHANISM	Pearson Correlation	.637**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	140	140	
OCTAPAC CULTURE	Pearson Correlation	.574**	.598**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	140	140	140

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

According to table 6, all the three elements of HRD Climate are significantly related to each other. Hence **HO** under study is selected.

Findings and Conclusion

The basic objective of this study was to evaluate the extent of HRD climate prevailing in Private schools of Srinagar district. The findings of the present study indicate the following.

Overall there exists relatively good level of HRD Climate in private schools of Srinagar district.

- ❖ **General HRD climate** in the present Study sample is of slightly above average level. The factors like helpfulness; attitude of the staff to discuss personal problems freely with their supervisors and favourable psychological climate for self-development have contributed to keep the climate somehow at higher level.
- ❖ Staff perceived **OCTAPAC culture** in private schools at a relatively good level. The study signifies that openness of staff with their subordinates and superiors and attitude of collaboration have contributed to keep the OCTAPAC culture still at upper level.
- ❖ It is identified that **HRD Mechanism/HRD sub-systems** in Private schools of district is at a significantly good level.
- There is significant relation ship between the three elements of HRD climate in private schools of District Srinagar.

The present study reveals that there is still a substantial scope for improvement of various aspects of HRD climate in Private schools of district Srinagar. Some of these aspects along with broad **suggestions** are:

- The school administrator’s commitment should be increased towards overall responsiveness to HRD function.
- The factor that requisite more attention are, commitment of seniors about development of subordinates (teachers), performance appraisal, firm personnel policies that show high concern for staff would go long way in creating better general climate in Private schools of district Srinagar.

- The management should draw its attention in bringing reforms in training and development, rewards and employee welfare.
- In creating favourable OCTAPAC culture management should put sincere efforts to entrench the values of confrontation, autonomy, authenticity and proactivity in Private schools of district Srinagar

Future Scope of Study

The present study was limited to assess the perception of teachers towards the HRD climate prevalent in private schools of Srinagar district only due to time, while such kind of study can be done in all types of organizations where the human resource is the backbone of the organization. It also can be expanded to more districts, regions, state and countries. It can also be extended to know the perceptual difference in Male and Female, higher income and lower income group, senior and junior employees and so on. Against this background, the present study can be extended to include other districts and other organizations as well with a higher sample at state/national level so that a wider picture of the HRD climate can be brought to front.

Limitations of the Study

Like other studies the present study also is not free from limitations and some of them are mentioned below:

- 1: The present study was confined to study the HRD climate prevailing in the private schools of Srinagar District only.
- 2: The findings may not be same all over India, since the teachers' perception is likely to vary depending upon the prevalent environment.
- 3: The sample size was restricted to 140 teachers belonging to only 6 different Private schools of district Srinagar due to the paucity of time and adequate financial resources.

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